

EXO GENES OF *RHIZOBIUM RADIOBACTER* 36 AND THEIR CHARACTERIZATION

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Bacteria of *Rhizobium* genus are characterized with synthesis exopolysaccharides (EPS), which play a crucial role in cell defense in abiotic stress, such as salinity, drought, heavy metals exposure etc. [1, 2]. Production of EPS by *Rhizobium* are controlled by a set of specific genes, such as *exo* genes [2]. The *exo* genes are a set of genes responsible for the biosynthesis, polymerization, and export of exopolysaccharides. The specific genes can vary depending on the *Rhizobium* strain. As reported in our previous research [2], a gene-cluster consisting of *exoK* and *exoM* are responsible for EPS macromolecule formation in *R. radiobacter*.

In this research, it was aimed to identify *exoM* and *exoK* genes of bacterial strain *R. radiobacter* 36.

Identification and expression of EPS gene-cluster consisting of *exoM* and *exoK* was evaluated in different cultivation conditions. *R. radiobacter* 36 incubated in both 0% and 2.0% NaCl supplemented medium, and the cell biomass and EPS were isolated for further evaluation. Presence of 2.0% NaCl negatively impacts on expression EPS gene-cluster and EPS formation [2]. *exoM* and *exoK* genes were identified in this research (Figure). This finding correlates with our earlier study that out of a wide variety *exo* genes, namely *exoM*, *exoK*, *exoT*, *exoW*, *exoS*, only *exoK* and *exoM* are peculiar to *R. radiobacter* species [2]. In presence of 2.0% NaCl the biomass formation and EPS synthesis decreased. This finding suggests that salt-stress down-regulates expression of *exoM* and *exoK* genes, and therefore the synthesis of EPS decreases. In conclusion, EPS biosynthesis by *R. rhizobium* 36 to be regulated by EPS gene-cluster consisting of two genes, *exoM* and *exoK*.

Figure. Identification of *exo* genes of *R. radiobacter* 36 strain. 1 – markers; 2 – *exoK* (NaCl free); 3 – *exoK* (NaCl supplemented); 4 – *exoM* (NaCl free); 5 – *exoM* (NaCl supplemented); 6 – 16S RNA

In our previous research with another strain of the same species, namely *R. radiobacter* SZ4S7S14 exhibited identification of both *exoK* and *exoM* genes in salt-stress and these genes took part in the EPS macromolecular formation in presence of 2.0% NaCl [2]. Comparing two

these strains, *R. radiobacter* 36 and *R. radiobacter* SZ4S7S14 it can be concluded that *exoK* and *exoM* genes expression depends genotypic peculiarities of the bacterial strains, which needs further elucidation with involvement of genome and RNA-transcriptome sequencing.

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